

**IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF PROFESSIONAL
COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN TALENTED STUDENTS**

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Abstract: This article is devoted to improving the methodology of developing the professional competence of gifted students. The role of methodological approaches in the formation and development of professional competence, the effectiveness of using modern educational technologies and innovative methods are analyzed. The author shows ways to achieve professional growth by directing students to practical activities, taking into account their personal abilities. The research results serve to propose new methodological methods and approaches in working with gifted students.

Key words: Talented students, professional competence, educational technologies, innovative methods, personal ability, practical activity, methodology, pedagogical approach.

Introduction.

Today, the development of society increases the need for qualified specialists with the ability to think innovatively. From this point of view, the issue of developing professional competence of talented students is of urgent importance. Talented students as the main subject of the educational process, to maximally reveal their intellectual and creative potential and to prepare them for professional activity is one of the important tasks of modern pedagogy.

In today's educational process, it is important to direct talented students to professional activities by using innovative methods and technologies, introducing approaches aimed at the development of personal abilities. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure a balance between practical activities, theoretical knowledge and skills in the development of professional competence.

In this article, the scientific-theoretical basis of development of professional competence of talented students, methodical approaches and ways of effective use of innovative tools are explained. Recommendations for improving the methodology were also developed during the educational process.

Literature analysis.

The issue of developing professional competence in gifted students is one of the topics widely studied in the field of pedagogy and psychology. The research conducted in this direction is of great importance in determining the theoretical

foundations of professional competence and developing methods of its development.

In pedagogical literature, the term professional competence is mainly interpreted as the ability of a person to effectively use knowledge, skills and abilities in professional activities. Researchers such as J. Raven (2000), A. Markova (1996), E. F. Zeer (2009) define competence as a set of social and individual abilities that serve to improve a person's professional skills. Their work shows the development of students' intellectual and creative potential as an important factor in the formation of competence.

In national studies, in particular, in the works of S. Ganiev, S. Turgunov and L. T. Kadirova, the role of innovative technologies in the formation of professional competence and the methods of developing personal abilities have been studied. They emphasize the effectiveness of practice-based approaches in education and the integration of modern information technologies into the educational process.

In addition, approaches based on international experience have their place. For example, V. Hutmacher (1997) identifies the main factors in the development of competence as increasing the activity of a person, forming responsibility and developing the ability to make independent decisions.

The analysis of the literature shows that an individual approach is important in working with gifted students, taking into account their personal characteristics. Also, the issue of improving the educational process through the use of modern educational technologies has been widely covered by researchers. Based on this, this article offers an effective methodology for developing professional competence.

Discussion.

Development of professional competence of talented students is one of the strategic tasks of the educational process. The main factors and methodical approaches identified during the research show that it is possible to increase the effectiveness of professional competence formation by using modern educational technologies and innovative pedagogical methods.

First, an individual approach is important in preparing talented students for professional activities. This requires consideration of students' interests, abilities, and capabilities. Especially in practice-based education, directing students' theoretical knowledge to solving real problems develops their ability to think analytically.

Secondly, as it was determined in the research, it is effective to combine group and individual training in the formation of professional competence. In group work, students develop the skills of mutual exchange of ideas and cooperation, and in individual classes, they have the opportunity to improve their knowledge and skills independently.

Thirdly, the introduction of innovative technologies creates new opportunities in the development of professional competence. In particular, the use of information and communication technologies improves communication skills of students, organizes the process of independent education and helps to develop their creative abilities.

At the same time, the literature analysis shows that responsibility and motivation play an important role in the formation of professional competence. The use of mechanisms that encourage students to be active and pedagogical tools that increase motivation accelerates their professional growth.

The results presented during the discussion serve to create an effective methodology for working with gifted students. These approaches allow maximum development of students' personal abilities and successful preparation for professional activities. Therefore, in the future, it is necessary to carry out additional research on the implementation of these methods and the evaluation of their effectiveness.

Conclusion.

This study is devoted to the issue of improving the methodology of developing professional competence in talented students, and the main results are summarized as follows:

1. Factors of formation of professional competence: In working with gifted students, taking into account their individual abilities, interests and opportunities, integrated approaches to the educational process are effective. The combination of theoretical knowledge and practical activities serves the professional development of students.

2. Methodical approaches: The use of innovative educational technologies and information and communication tools ensures independent learning and formation of creative abilities among students. And the combination of group and individual training supports mutual cooperation and personal development together.

3. Practical significance: Methodological recommendations presented in this article serve to increase the efficiency of working with gifted students.

Approaches aimed at increasing motivation and responsibility are especially important in the formation of professional competence.

Research results show that it is important to combine innovative and personal approaches when working with gifted students. In the future, it is necessary to develop new pedagogical solutions by testing this methodology in practice and evaluating its results. This makes it possible to improve the quality of training of talented students for professional activities in the educational system.

References:

1. Zeer, E. F. (2009). Psixologiya professional'noy deyatel'nosti. Moskva: Akademiya.
2. Markova, A. K. (1996). Psixologiya professionalizma. Moskva: Znanie.
3. Raven, J. (2000). Competence in Modern Society: Its Identification, Development, and Assessment. Oxford: Psychologists Press.
4. Turg'unov, S. (2018). Pedagogik innovatsiyalar: nazariya va amaliyot. Toshkent: Ilmiy izlanishlar markazi.
5. Hutmacher, V. (1997). Key Competencies for Europe. Report of the Symposium on Key Competencies. European Council.
6. Freire, P. (1970). Pedagogy of the Oppressed. New York: Continuum.
7. Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).
8. Xudoynazarov, E. M. (2019). Didactic possibilities of oral exercises in forming initial classes pupils' mathematical thinking activity. Eastern European Scientific Journal, Ausgabe. Germany, (1-2019), 249.
9. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang 'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. Молодые ученые, 1(13), 32-37.

